

APEL - WB

ACCREDITATION OF PRIOR EXPERIENTIAL LEARNING CAPACITY-BUILDING
IN THE WESTERN BALKANS

ERASMUS-EDU-2025- CBHE-STRAND-3 / PROJECT NO. 101236402

NEWSLETTER

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REPUBLIC OF KOSOVO
MINISTRY OF EDUCATION, SCIENCE,
TECHNOLOGY AND INNOVATION

LOGOS University College, Universiteti i Shkodrës “Luigj Gurakuqi”, Agjencia e Sigurimit të Cilësisë në Arsimin e Lartë (ASCAL), Universiteti i Prishtinës, RIT Kosovo (A.U.K) College, Haskolinn a Akureyri, Tallinn University, Ministria e Arsimit e Republikës së Shqipërisë, Univerzitet u Sarajevu, Panepistimio Patron, Centar za informiranje i priznavanje dokumenata iz područja visokog obrazovanja (CIP), Ministry of Education Science Technology and Innovation in Republic of Kosovo

This issue:

**Kick-Off and First General Management Meeting
Dissemination & Opening Event**

APEL-WB Partners

Partner contributions

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A NOTE FROM THE COORDINATOR

Dear readers

Welcome to the very first issue of APEL-WB Project Newsletter, the biannual publication of our ERASMUS-EDU-2025-CBHE-STRAND-3 project, focused on strengthening the role of higher education as a driver of societal change, development and growth, with a particular attention on supporting the underprivileged groups. APEL-WB brings together 12 partner institutions, including two Ministries of Education, 2 national agencies for accreditation and evaluation of higher education, and 8 HEIs from Albania, Kosovo, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Greece, Estonia, and Iceland. The project will be implemented over a period of three years, from October 2025 to September 2028, across 3 countries in the Western Balkans.

In the natural sciences, one of the most important concepts is the frame of reference. We cannot say whether a body is at rest or in motion without asking the question, “In relation to what?” The key phrase here is “in relation to what?” The main goal of this project is to introduce, within higher education in three countries - Albania, Kosovo, and Bosnia and Herzegovina - a new perspective in the educational system: the recognition of credits acquired through non-formal learning. “In relation to what?” And it leads us to ask: What will be our frame of reference in this project?

Our frame of reference is the European Higher Education Area, guided by the policy framework of “Lifelong Learning for All,” adopted by the OECD Ministers of Education as early as 1996. Conceived as a social mandate to ensure equitable and inclusive opportunities, lifelong learning requires the coordinated functioning of multiple subsystems within education. The Lisbon Recognition Convention (Article IV.8, Council of Europe & UNESCO, 1997) underscores the importance of recognizing learning acquired through self-education, work, and life experiences, and highlights the necessity of accrediting such learning. This means not discriminating against knowledge simply because it was acquired through experiential, informal, or non-traditional pathways. In the spirit of the Lisbon Recognition Convention, “competence, knowledge, and skills may also be acquired in other ways, such as through self-education or through work and life experience.”

As noted by the Federal Ministry of Education, Science and Research of the Republic of Austria, learning gained through work-life experience or self-education can form part of non-traditional qualifications, provided that a national system formally recognizes them as such. The project will contribute to an evidence-based approach in the identification and development of support measure for people who have non-formal or informal learning experiences to get their education recognized in order to facilitate access to Higher Education in their Country, in WB and in Europe.

Thank you to European Education and Culture Executive Agency, for the belief and the support! Thank you all our partners! Within this project, we need to learn from each-other, cooperate and exchange experiences. We need to work on the spirit of Erasmus.

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APEL - WB Kick-Off and First General Management Meeting Dissemination & Opening Event

**PROJECT LAUNCH BRINGS
TOGETHER KEY PARTNERS
FROM THE WB AND THE EU**

From November 20 to 22, 2025, the amphitheatre hall of LOGOS University College hosted the Kick-Off and First General Management Meeting of the APEL-WB project. The events convened university leaders, academics, administrative staff, and representatives from all partner institutions.

The consortium brings together higher education institutions, Ministries of Education, and National Agencies for Quality Assurance in Higher Education from Albania, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Estonia, Iceland, Greece, and Kosovo, all of which actively contributed to the discussions and outcomes.

**A NEW EDUCATIONAL INITIATIVE
IN THE HIGHER EDUCATION
SECTOR IN WB**

The Kick-off and First General Management Meeting of the APEL-WB project marked the launch of a significant educational initiative in the HE sector. The project focuses on the recognition and accreditation of prior experiential learning, aiming to strengthen access, inclusion, and quality assurance mechanisms across higher education systems in the Western Balkans.

It highlighted the strong commitment of 4 educational authorities from 3 different countries not associated with the program in the WB, The Agency for Quality Assurance in HE and Ministry of Education of Republic of Albania, Centre for Information and Recognition of Qualifications in HE, Mostar, Bosna i Hercegovina and Ministry of Education, Science, Technology and Innovation of Republic of Kosovo, in cooperation with 8 HEIs, intend to make a significant step in the landscape of legal admission and accreditation of competencies in higher education system.

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In the Western Balkans (WB), Accreditation of Prior Experiential Learning (APEL) remains underutilized. The proposed project aims to bridge this gap by institutionalizing APEL in WB as a systemic-change cornerstone of an inclusive higher education. Aligning with European Commission and WB priorities - sustainable growth and knowledge-driven economies- the project proposes a comprehensive framework inspired by best European practices.

APEL-WB ACCREDITATION OF PRIOR EXPERIENTIAL LEARNING CAPACITY- BUILDING IN THE WESTERN BALKANS

The project aims to prepare the Western Balkans for expanding lifelong learning opportunities. It seeks to enhance lifelong learning and workforce qualifications by creating an efficient, comprehensive, and institutionalized system for recognizing and accrediting credits based on prior experiential learning in Higher Education Institutions in the region, aligning with the standards and practices of the European Higher Education Area.

Mr. Dimitrios Moschos, APEL-WB Project Officer at the European Education and Culture Executive Agency (EACEA), addressed the audience online. Mr. Moschos reiterated the alignment of APEL-WB with EU higher education priorities and stressed the importance of sound project management, timely delivery of outputs, and adherence to EU standards throughout the implementation process.

Addressing the event on-line: Mr. Dimitrios MOSCHOS, Project Officer, together with his colleague, Una Duzelic / European Education and Culture Executive Agency (EACEA)

Group Photo: Kick-Off Meeting
Tirana, LOGOS, November 20, 2025

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APEL-WB Partner

The mission of LOGOS University College is to serve society through education, research, innovation, fostering individual development to transform their lives; ensuring student success in a global environment; providing academic services and developing an inclusive community.

LOGOS UNIVERSITY COLLEGE

LOGOS University College leads the network of partners in this project and also is lead beneficiary for Work Package 1 “Project Management & Coordination”

Prof. Konstantinos Giakoumi and Prof. Artur Ribaj

Dr. Valbona Nathanaili

Adv. Venian (Naum) Mile

Partner contribution

The meeting began with a warm welcome address delivered by Prof. Dr. Ilia Ninka, Rector of LOGOS University College, who emphasized the importance of collaboration, institutional commitment, and the shared vision driving the APEL-WB initiative. The Kick-off Meeting continued with an overview of the project objectives and main milestones presented by Dr. Valbona Nathanaili, Project Coordinator and Prof. Konstantinos Giakoumis, Contact Person. The session included contributions from Prof. Artur Ribaj, leader of WP1 – Project Management & Coordination, who guided the discussion and officially launched the draft Project Management Plan.

Prof. Tonin Gjuraraj, Rector, Universiteti i Shkodrës “Luigj Gurakuqi”

APEL-WB Partner

The University of Shkodra “Luigj Gurakuqi” aims to be a key actor in promoting knowledge, science, and community and intellectual values through transparent communication and information sharing. Its mission is to educate highly qualified specialists and prepare new researchers by creating, transmitting, developing, and safeguarding knowledge through teaching, scientific research, and service.

The University of Shkodra “Luigj Gurakuqi” (Albania) was introduced by Assoc. Prof. Bresena Kopliku, who presented the institution’s profile and its commitment to supporting the implementation of APEL-WB.

Universiteti i Shkodrës “Luigj Gurakuqi”

Partner contribution

As a partner institution, the University of Shkodra “Luigj Gurakuqi” expressed its strong willingness to be part of the APEL-WB initiative and its full commitment to actively supporting the project’s implementation and future activities.

The University of Shkodra “Luigj Gurakuqi” was represented by Assoc. Prof. Bresena Kopliku, Assoc. Prof. Ardita Borici, and Mr. Erard Curcija, who participated actively in the Kick-off Meeting sessions.

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APEL-WB Partner

The mission of the ASCAL is to: Ensuring quality in higher education through external objective, and independent evaluation; Maintaining quality standards; Promoting and improving the quality of higher education institutions and study programs they offer.

Assoc. Prof. Anisa Subashi
Director, ASCAL

Agjencia e Sigurimit të Cilësisë në Arsimin e Lartë (ASCAL)

Partner contribution

An important contribution to the APEL-WB Kick-off Meeting came from Mr. Erion Xhako, who presented the Quality Assurance Agency in Higher Education, highlighting its role and relevance within the national quality assurance system.

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APEL-WB Partner

The mission of University of Prishtina is based on academic development, scientific and artistic research, and the provision of higher education through programs of strategic and developmental interest to the Republic of Kosovo. The University enables the mobility of programs, students, and academic staff on an ongoing basis, intending to reach the international level and competition in the market.

Prof. Naser Zabeli presented the draft D6.1 APEL-WB Sustainability and Dissemination Strategy and Plan, outlining the key actions for ensuring the project’s long-term impact, visibility, and stakeholder engagement.

Universiteti i Prishtinës

University of Prishtina is lead beneficiary for Work Package 6 “Dissemination and Exploitation”

Partner contribution

The University of Prishtina contributed actively to the Kick-off Meeting as the lead beneficiary for Work Package 6, “Dissemination and Exploitation.” The team presented two key deliverables: the revised D6.1 APEL-WB Sustainability and Dissemination Strategy and Plan and D6.2 APEL-WB Templates and Visual Materials Used in the APEL-WB Project. Through this contribution, the University of Prishtina reaffirmed its strong commitment to ensuring the project’s visibility, sustainability, and long-term impact across the Western Balkans.

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About RIT Kosovo (A.U.K)

APEL-WB Partner

RIT Kosovo (A.U.K) will deliver an outstanding American education for students from Kosovo and the world through innovative curricular, experiential, and research programs in a student-centered culture. Our students acquire expertise, knowledge, and values that prepare them to contribute to the global society.

RIT Kosovo (A.U.K) College

Partner contribution

RIT Kosovo (A.U.K.) College brings valuable expertise and shows a strong long-term commitment to advancing the objectives of APEL-WB, particularly in strengthening the recognition of prior experiential and non-formal learning in higher education across the Western Balkans. Their continued engagement will play an important role in supporting the project's development and future activities.

Edmond Muhaxheri, Assistant Professor & CFO, and **Lavon Bajrami**, Chief Administrative Officer and Adjunct Faculty, represented their institution at the APEL-WB Kick-off Meeting. Both contributed actively throughout the event, offering insightful ideas and constructive suggestions that enriched the discussions within the working groups and plenary sessions.

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APEL-WB Partner

As a leading research hub in Northern Iceland, the University of Akureyri is dedicated to excellence in teaching, innovation, and research. Its mission is to create an inclusive & multicultural academic environment that promotes understanding, respect, & collaboration. Through high-quality teaching, impactful research, & active engagement with society, the University seeks to contribute to regional development while addressing global challenges.

Prof. Markus Hermann Meckl offered an insightful overview of Iceland’s long-standing experience, frameworks, & institutional practices in validating prior learning, provided the consortium with valuable perspectives and comparative examples that can inform the development of APEL approaches across the WB.

Haskolinn a Akureyri

University of Akureyri is lead beneficiary for Work Package 2 “Strategic research”

Partner contribution

University of Akureyri participated in the project’s kick-off meeting in Albania and has led the initiation of work packages under its responsibility. This includes starting the distribution of questionnaire to collect data on the existing conditions for recognition and accreditation recognition of prior learning (RAPL) within Higher Education (HE) in the Western Balkans and preparation of the training programme that will take place in Akureyri as part of the project’s capacity-building activities.

The University of Akureyri was represented by Prof. Markus Hermann Meckl, Dr. Stéphanie Barillé, Anna Karen Úlfarsdóttir and Heiða Kristín Jónsdóttir.

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APEL-WB Partner

Tallinn University is a modern and dynamic research university in Estonia with a leading role in promoting an intelligent lifestyle through education, research, and a unique collaboration across disciplines. We view an intelligent lifestyle as making research-based decisions in order to improve society in general and the well-being of its citizens.

Dr. Mari-Liis Lind, Head of Studies at the School of Educational Sciences, delivered an engaging presentation on “Assuring the Quality of the APEL Process: Roles and Responsibilities of Key Stakeholders,” offering valuable insights into how institutions can build transparent, reliable, and learner-centered recognition procedures

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Tallinn University

Tallinn University is lead beneficiary for Work Package 3 “Structuring APEL Assessment Units at Partner Universities”

Mari-Liis Lind and **Katerina Chikhran** presented “Practical Approaches and Case Studies in the Validation of Prior Informal Learning,” highlighting concrete examples and effective practices drawn from the Estonian experience.

Partner contribution

Tallinn University (TLU) has actively contributed to the launch and early implementation of the APEL-WB project. During the initial phase, the university supported project activities and fostered cooperation among partners.

A key achievement has been the preparation and signing of the Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) and Inter-Institutional Agreements (IIA) with APEL-WB partner institutions, like University of Shkodra “Luigj Gurakuqi” and RIT Kosovo (A.U.K) College.

TLU has played a vital role in introducing the Estonian context and gaining insights into partner countries’ approaches to the Accreditation of Prior Experiential Learning (APEL). This included mapping existing recognition practices and discussing the opportunities and challenges of APEL implementation.

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Ms. Mirela Kumbaro, Minister of Education

APEL-WB Partner

The Ministry of Education is responsible for developing national education policies, revising curricula, and ensuring high-quality, inclusive learning across all levels of the education system. It oversees educational institutions, reviews the regulatory framework, and coordinates initiatives that support student development and promote a modern, future-oriented education sector.

Mr. Vangjush Stavro, Director of the General Directorate for the Development of Higher Education and Scientific Research

Ms. Matilda Bulku introduced the Ministry's role, priorities, and ongoing initiatives related to the lifelong learning pathways.

Ministria e Arsimit e Republikës së Shqipërisë

Partner contribution

Ministry of Education of the Republic of Albania participated in the project's kick-off meeting. **Mr. Vangjush Stavro**, Director of the General Directorate for the Development of Higher Education and Scientific Research, **Ms. Edlira Përfundi**, Director of the Directorate of Higher Education Programmes and **Ms. Matilda Bulku**, Head of the Sector for Administration, Monitoring, and Evaluation of Higher Education Institutions strengthened the dialogue between higher education institutions and national authorities, underlining the importance of policy alignment for the successful development of APEL processes.

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APEL-WB Partner

University of Sarajevo is a large and complex public institution, comprising 22 Faculties, 3 Academies, and 5 research institutes. Associate members of the University include the National and University Library of BiH, Gazi Husrev-bey's Library and the National Museum, as well as other units.

Merisa Kurtanović, Berina Smajlović Doljančić and Sead Berberović

The consortium, under the guidance of University of Sarajevo Team, discussed the Protocol for the Selection Procedure of the External Quality Evaluation Expert as well as the call for the selection of the Service Provider responsible for establishing and maintaining the project's website.

Berina Smajlović Doljančić, Semir Đulić and Prof. Dženana Husremović

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Univerzitet u Sarajevu

University of Sarajevo is lead beneficiary for Work Package 5 "Quality assurance"

Project LOGO, courtesy of Prof. Selma Rizvić

Partner contribution

Quality assurance was a central focus of the APEL-WB Kick-off Meeting. Prof. Dr. Dženana Husremović, Vice-Rector for Teaching and Students Affairs, guided the consortium through the Discussion of the Quality Monitoring Action Plan, emphasizing the importance of systematic oversight in ensuring the reliability and transparency of APEL processes. The meeting also included a thorough review and approval of the members of the Quality Monitoring Committee, formalizing the structure that will supervise internal quality throughout the project's implementation.

πλοία τοποθετημένα σε κατάλληλα φορεία (ολκούς) αποφεύγονταν ο περίπλους της Πελοποννήσου. Ο πιθανώς κατά τον βο αι... ρισκόταν σε λειτου...

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APEL-WB Partner

University of Patras (UPatras) is one of the most distinguished universities nationally and internationally owing to its manifold and innovative action in the fields of Natural Sciences, Engineering, Health Sciences, Humanities, Social and Economic Sciences, along with its remarkable research activity.

“Knowledge is not enough without acquiring Education”

Prof. Thanassis Karalis, delivered the institutional presentation of the University of Patras, emphasizing the institution’s experience, expertise, and strong commitment to supporting the development and piloting phase of APEL-WB.

Panepistimio Patron

Panepistimio Patron is lead beneficiary for Work Package 4 “Development: Setting up and piloting of the portfolio”

Partner contribution

Under WP4 Development: Setting up and Piloting of the Portfolio, **Danae Tsantila** from the University of Patras presented the initial framework and key methodological steps for designing and implementing the APEL portfolio across partner institutions. Her contribution offered practical guidance on structuring the portfolio as a central tool for recognizing prior experiential learning.

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APEL-WB Partner

CIP, as an expert and professional institution of BiH, transfers knowledge and skills, provides information, advice, opinions and recommendations to higher education institutions, competent educational authorities, administrative authorities, other legal and natural persons, represents BiH in the work of the ENIC/NARIC network, in the creation of European and global policies in the field of recognition, participates in domestic and international projects.

Ms. Gordana Šolaja introduced the institution's role and expertise in the field of information and recognition of higher education documents.

Centar za informiranje i priznavanje dokumenata iz područja visokog obrazovanja (CIP)

Partner contribution

As a project partner, CIP contributes to APEL-WB with its long-standing expertise in improving and facilitating the recognition of higher education qualifications, supporting academic mobility, and strengthening the development of higher education in Bosnia and Herzegovina.

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APEL-WB Partner

The Ministry of Education, Science and Technology of Kosovo is a government institution responsible for the development, organization and supervision of the education system, as well as for the promotion of science and technology in the country. This ministry aims to provide a quality and appropriate education for all citizens of Kosovo, including preschool education, primary, secondary and higher education.

Ministry of Education, Science, Technology and Innovation in Republic of Kosovo

Partner contribution

Through its policies, the Ministry of Education, Science and Technology tries to improve the quality of education and encourage young people to choose different scientific and technological fields, helping to build an educated and prepared society for today's and future challenges.

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